

What steps to take when AV is yet to become a priority for your organisation

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Digital Preservation at Oxford and Cambridge (DPOC)

- Collaboration between Bodleian Libraries, Oxford & Cambridge University Library
- Research project (2.5 years), finishing December 2018
- Outreach & Training, Policy & Planning, Technical Fellows

A lot of skills (but still not enough)

Skills, knowledge & experience

data management
digital content creation and production
digital forensics
digital humanities & media arts
online delivery system development
programming languages
project management (waterfall & agile)
policy development
broadcast (radio)
risk management
archive management
records management
information legislation
information systems
event management and production
supporting & managing digitisation programmes
collections management
communication skills
systems integration
still image digitisation (incl. photography)
international digital preservation networks
knowledge of digital preservation systems
grant writing
library/archive metadata standards
web archiving
publishing research articles

Qualifications

Museum Studies
Archival Science
Records Management
Communications
Photography
Multimedia
Computing
Information Science
Information Systems Admin
Music
Digital Preservation (Train-the-Trainer)

New skills we had to develop

maturity modelling
business case development
research data management
quantitative research methods
(survey construction and statistical analysis)
advocacy

Still missing

Moving image (film and video) specialist/engineer

Audio digitisation technician/engineer

Conservator (audiovisual carriers)

High-level collection profiling (digital content)

Class	Type	Description
1	Born-digital personal and corporate records	Digital archives of significant individuals or institutions
2	Born-digital university records	Selected records of the University (including CUL)
3	Research outputs	Research data, research publications, electronic and digitised theses, scholarly digital editions, supplementary research relating to digitised content and associated materials
4	Published born-digital content	Web archives, eBooks, born-digital maps, born-digital music, ephemera, published born-digital content on carriers and copies of electronic subscription materials (archival and/or access copies, as permitted by agreements) etc.
5	Digitised content	Digitised image content: Two-dimensional (2D) photography and three-dimensional (3D) imaging etc. Digitised audiovisual content: Moving image (film and video) and sound recordings etc.
6	In-house created content	Photography and videography of events and lectures, photos of conservation treatments etc.

But what about AV...

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5	Digitised content	Digitised image content: Two-dimensional (2D) photography and three-dimensional (3D) imaging etc. Digitised audiovisual content: Moving image (film and video) and sound recordings etc. + digital/analogue AV (on carriers)
6	In-house created content	Photography and videography of events and lectures, photos of conservation treatments etc.

Class 3 – research outputs

The screenshot shows the Apollo repository interface. The main heading is "Lecture by Dr Stephen Pax Leonard for the World Oral Literature Project Occasional Lecture Series". A search bar is visible at the top right. On the left, there is a "Browse" sidebar with categories like "All of Apollo", "Communities & Collections", "Authors", "Titles", "Keywords", "Type", and "This Collection". The main content area includes a "View / Open Files" section with links to a PDF presentation (157M), a PDF poster (989Kb), and an MP3 audio file (81Mb). Below this is an "Abstract" section with a short biography of Dr Stephen Pax Leonard.

Aijakko Mitq: drum songs [Video file]. (.wav video file)

The screenshot shows the Kymata Atlas Surface Viewer interface. The main heading is "Atlas - The Kymata Atlas". The URL is "https://kymata.org/atlas.html". The interface includes a search bar and navigation links for "START KYMATA", "DOCUMENTATION", "PARTNERS", and "ABOUT". The main content area displays a 3D brain model with highlighted regions in orange and white. The MNI coordinate is [-39, 16, 35] and the region is identified as "LEFT caudal middle frontal gyrus". The text "Fo (instantaneous) ID VDT8Q" is visible on the right side of the brain model.

Video Screen Capture still of the Kymata Atlas Surface Viewer

Class 5 – digitised content

UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE

University of Cambridge > Video & Audio > Collections > Royal Commonwealth Society Film Collection

Video & Audio | Institutions | **Collections** | Media | Statistics

Royal Commonwealth Society Film Collection

Collection | Statistics

Created: 2013-08-05 14:30
Institution: Cambridge University Library

Description: The Royal Commonwealth Society Film Collection contains twenty-one original amateur films made primarily in Africa, South and South East Asia, Canada, Europe, the Caribbean, and the US. It also contains viewing copies of three Ministry of Information and government-commissioned films. The films have been recently digitized, catalogued and researched and are now available for viewing on the Streaming Media Service, University of Cambridge (see Media items below).

The original footage belongs mainly to the Tyms Film Collection with seventeen 16mm and 8mm colour and b/w films made in Africa, South and South East Asia and West Indies between the mid-1920s and the early 1960s. Sir Frederick Tyms (1889-1987) worked on the development of air routes in Africa and India, before becoming


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CU-857-MacBook-Pro:audiovisual s21285 exitool -ops largefilesupport=1 -r Goodbye_India_uncompressed.mov
Exitool Version Number : 28.43
File Name : Goodbye_India_uncompressed.mov
Directory :
File Size : 64 GB
File Modification Date/Line : 2012:07:19 11:09:59+0100
File Access Date/Line : 2012:09:16 13:16:02+0100
File Inode Change Date/Line : 2012:09:16 13:04:25+0100
File Permissions : rwxr-xr-x
File Type : MOV
File Type Extension : mov
MIME Type : video/quicktime
Major Brand : Apple QuickTime (.MOV/.QT)
Minor Version : 2004.6.0
Compatible Brands : 00
Movie Data Size : 08483261978
Movie Data Offset : 36
Movie Header Version : 0
Create Date : 2012:07:19 10:19:09
Modify Date : 2012:07:19 10:19:09
Time Scale : 25
Duration : 0:54:01
Preferred Date : 0
Preferred Volume : 100.00%
Preview Time : 0
Preview Duration : 0
Poster Time : 0
Selection Time : 0
Selection Duration : 0
Current Time : 0
Next Track ID : 0
Track Header Version : 0
Track Create Date : 2012:07:19 10:19:09
Track Modify Date : 2012:07:19 10:19:09
Track ID : 1
Track Duration : 0:54:01
Track Layer : 0
Track Volume : 0.00%
Image Width : 720
Image Height : 576
Clean Aperture Dimensions : 788x576
Production Aperture Dimensions : 788x576
Encoded Pixels Dimensions : 720x576
Graphics Mode : iRGB4
Op Color : 0 0 0
Compressor ID : 24v2
Vendor ID : Unknown (TELE)
Source Image Width : 720
Source Image Height : 576
```

Royal Commonwealth Society collection

Class 6 – in-house created content

Lines of Thought, exhibition video still (2016), Cambridge University Library

<https://youtu.be/ic8jl2yHpGc>

Class 7 – digital (and analogue) audiovisual content

Vickers Archive, Cambridge University Library. Photos: Somaya Langley

Priorities (and case studies)

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Challenges (too many to get to the end of the list)

- no AV DAMS
- no AV engineers/specialists
- researchers using consumer devices to record AV
- research data repository – doesn't factor in cost of preservation
- differing retention periods
- no EDRMS
- no digital archivists
- no dedicated funding (for digital preservation or AV)
- still consider digital preservation a technical problem
- lack of policies
- no in-house AV QC skills
- too many other high-priority issues
- assume archivists and curators can digitise AV
- senior leadership changes
- missing PSPG
- no digital preservation system (yet)
- no dedicated digital preservation staff
- no single acquisition stream
- digital literacy is low (after December)
- (donors get different responses depending on different pathways)
- etc...

What we've done

Organisational Infrastructure

*Broken record:
banging the drum
(repeatedly)*

Resources Framework

Technical Infrastructure

Three-legged stool model for digital preservation

Gather the data – digital preservation survey

NDSA Levels of Digital Preservation	Level 0 <i>(doesn't exist)</i>		Level 1		Level 2		Level 3		Level 4	
	UK	Rest of world	UK	Rest of world	UK	Rest of world	UK	Rest of world	UK	Rest of world
Storage and Geographic Location	9	7	10	11	7	12	1	10	3	16
File Fixity and Data Integrity	18	4	4	14	3	8	4	19	1	13
Information Security	8	6	12	16	4	5	3	22	3	10
Metadata	10	9	7	4	5	7	6	17	2	19
File Formats	14	7	6	7	5	15	4	16	1	12

<https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.26222>

Digital preservation survey (maturity)

Average NDSA Levels
of Digital Preservation

North America

Europe

Australasia

<https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.28129>

Digital preservation survey (resourcing)

<https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.28129>

What to do to make sure *AV* doesn't fall off the radar?

Embed it in policy

- *“Audiovisual content contained on both digital and analogue carriers is also covered by this Policy.”* – inaugural Digital Preservation Policy
- *“Analogue and digital materials held on carriers such as optical media, reel and tape etc. are stored in environmentally suitable conditions, according to international standards...”* – Collection care and conservation policy

Establish an AV community of practice

Department or Team	Role
Pendlebury Library of Music	Head of Music Collections
University Archives	Archivist, Cambridge University Press
Modern Manuscripts	Archivist, Royal Greenwich Observatory
Digital Initiatives and Strategy	Senior Developer
Office of Scholarly Communications	Repository Manager
Conservation and Collection Care	Senior Conservator
Digital Library Unit	Digital Library Coordinator
Digital Content Unit	Senior Photographic Technician
English Faculty Library	Head of Arts and Humanities Libraries
Centre of South Asian Studies Library	South Asian Studies Archivist

Other options

- a) **Piggy-back on other programme(s)**
(Save our Sounds – British Library)
- b) **One-off digitisation**
(Small ‘pot’ of funding or vendors approach us)
- c) **Transfer to another institution / repatriation**
- d) **Advocate internally & externally**
(Announce our issues to the community & if the community cares then...)
- e) **Forget about the analogue carriers and only focus on born-digital**
- f) **Embed ‘early stage’ AV needs into the Digital Preservation Strategy (in draft)**
(the need to develop an AV Digitisation and Preservation Strategy – including costings)
- g) **Insist on gradual skills development & knowledge-sharing**
(via an AV Community of Practice)
- h) **Do nothing**
- i) **All of the above?**
- j) **None of the above (and do something else instead)??**

Points (& your suggestions)

- Audiovisual has permeated our (digital) lives - there's no escape
- By 2021, video is estimated to take up 82% of all consumer internet traffic

What action(s) would you suggest?

Centre for South Asian Studies - AV collection items, University of Cambridge. Photo: Somaya Langley

Thank you

#dp0c

<http://www.dpoc.ac.uk>

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Cambridge University Libraries